

NIVA WP 3 –Statistics Poland interview

Date: 26 May 2021 - 13 h – 15 h

Location: Teams meeting

Stakeholder description

1. Organisation name: National Statistical Institute of Poland (NSI Poland)
2. Person name:
3. Person position /role :
 - Removed for privacy reasons: chief of agriculture department in NSI Poland
 - Removed for privacy reasons: researcher in IGIK (Institute of Geodesy and Cartography)
4. What is the general purpose of the organisation?

NSI Poland is in charge to produce official statistics for European level (Eurostat) or for domestic purposes.

5. What are the activities related to agriculture in general ? What are the activities requiring use of data about agriculture?

We produce crop production statistics at various periods of the year: July, September and end of the year. First ones are production forecasts whereas the statistics coming from final data after the end of the campaign are production appraisal. These statistics are about crop in arable land but also about horticulture and livestock. We have big pressure on cereal forecast in July (need from the market).

We conduct also the agricultural census based on the Integrated Farm Statistics for Europe. Last census was in 2020 and we are currently working to prepare the new one.

We also produce statistics on various topics, such as economic accounts, emissions....

User experience – User requirements

1. What current IACS data do you need?
 - Agricultural parcels

Yes, we use them. We are interested in the crop type but it is available only on farms with more than 10 ha (for diversification condition) whereas in Poland, there are lots of small farms (the average size is 11 ha). As a result, there is lot of missing data.

This is why NSI Poland and IGIK have been involved in 2 projects aiming to complement IACS data:

- The EOStat funded by ESA and aiming to crop recognition and agriculture activity monitoring: the agricultural parcel with its crop type is used as training or as validation data. NSI Poland is the main beneficiary of the project but PA has joined later and has proposed other topics (recognition of harvest, treatments, grassland)
- A project with the National Centre for Research and Development aiming also to crop monitoring, crop yield forecast. The main purpose is to provide infrastructure to process satellite data (S-3 for current monitoring, MODIS for the 20-yrs reference time series, S-1 for crop recognition)

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Centre_for_Research_and_Development

NSI Poland has its own inspectors making field visits, checking the crop type, the state of growth and assessing the yield, based on the observation of agro-techniques. The data from these field visits is not shared with PA (statistical secret); in addition, PA is not interested in yields.

We have an agreement with PA so we can get preliminary data from IACS (without validation) for our crop forecast by June –July and in September. We get final validated data only in March of following year.

NSI Poland has interest for long time series in order to identify the trends. Currently, these long time series are produced using Corine Land Cover data, extracting the pixels on arable land, computing vegetation index, aggregated the results on administrative units and applying machine learning to generate yields for selected crops and provide NSI statistics on crop yields.

With S-2 images (and IACS data), we will be able to improve yield forecast by extracting spectral signatures for a specific crop and not for the entire arable land (as it is now).

- Landscape features

This was part of the EOstat project: we tried to identify landscape features using S-2 images but the resolution was not fine enough for these small objects. Planet or even finer resolution images would have been necessary.

Currently, NSI Poland is not producing any statistics about these landscape features though we have some interest in nature reservoirs (but without needing deep detail).

- Animals

There is a Register of Animals that is managed by the PA (with support of veterinary service). It includes data about number of animals, their characteristics (race, birthdate ...) and the link to the farmer.

We use some data from this register to define our sampling frame for the agricultural census. Next year, we plan to use the register data as direct input.

We have also to provide indicators about emissions; for this we combine data about use of natural or chemical fertilizers (nitrate – phosphate – carbon) with crops and livestock in order to assess the emissions. It is relatively new.

- Beneficiaries

Yes, it is useful for the agricultural census. The IACS provide us the list of contact point for our survey. We get the means to contact and reach farmers: address, e-mail, telephone.

We compile data from IACS and from Ministry of Finances. You check data from various sources.

We are allowed to use these data only in the very specific case of agricultural census.

IACS data would be useful for other surveys and we can get it but with some limitations: typically, we don't get the farmer identification but just a random identifier on parcels. We can make the link between the parcel and the household but we don't get the localisation.

- Quality controls

We take PA data that is globally quite good (less than 2% of wrong declarations). This is negligible for our EO process (Random Forest): IACS data may be used as training data without issue. However, there may be some discrepancies; for instance, farmer has adapted to disaster events such as freezing or droughts.

We may also have different interpretations regarding the crop type code list; for instance, the IACS code list is not detailed up to the species; they just provide data about brassicae whereas we'd like to have distinction between broccoli, cauliflower ...

Regarding OTSC, inspectors just indicate the error type by a code but without providing the right value. This is a pity because we might use the OTSC data as validation data for our crop classification processors.

- Entitlements

This system does not apply in Poland, the Ministry is not in favour of it.

- Payments

Yes, we receive data for economic accounts that may be computed at regional or national levels.

1. What potential future IACS data do you need?

- Farm Registry

Yes, we have big requirements about use of fertilizers and Plant Protection Products (PPP). This data is necessary to compute our indicators about emissions.

Farmers have the obligation to record use of PPP but they generally do it in paper register. They are reluctant to move to digital. For NSI Poland, getting information from electronic register would be great.

There is a regulation about pesticides. Currently we use data from another register (inspection) that is not linked with IACS. From this register, we extract our sample: the list of farms with the crop we want to survey and then we collect data from the selected farm paper register. It has to be done every 5 years.

We have also interest in the use of fertilizers as this use influence the yield (for our crop forecast).

There is also an interest for the agricultural census that includes some core constant variables and some changing ones. Currently, there is interest about practices, methods of production, emissions. As data is not in IACS, we have to make surveys. Using EO data might also be a solution.

During the EOStat project, PA was willing to assess the harvest date. There is a legal obligation about not harvesting before a given date in some natural park but no data in IACS about this practice.

The Estonian company who was participating in the project has developed a tool kit for Estonia and for a few districts in Poland. However, as we were lacking of reference data for validation, we could not verify so we can't say if it is good or bad.

For crop yield modelling, even sample data from IACS about phenology would be useful (for validation); the information has to be attached to a given parcel.

- Crop classification & Traffic lights (EO monitoring)

Currently, NSI Poland is more advanced regarding EO processing than PA (PA has learnt from us); PA are only doing visual recognition of crops or practices.

- Geotagged photos

Yes, we are interested. We do the same: we take photos and we annotate them. We use them for visual recognition (if georeferenced) as independent reference data.

PA of Poland has developed a geotagged application.

- Agro-environmental indicators

Yes, we are interested.

For NSI Poland, the nitrate is difficult to be measured by Sentinel. In NIVA, the nitrate indicator doesn't measure the fertilizer use but the influence of crop rotation.

NSI Poland is interested under condition to be able to compute these indicators. NSI has also the role to design and compute indicators for the SDG.

Opinion about data sharing principles

1. What data do you think should be publicly available for use?

Igik: main progress would be to get data as soon as possible (and not after a year after the whole validation process). There are other limitations; for instance, it is not allowed to provide the parcel geometry without the crop.

NSI: as statistic office, we can get any IACS data.

NSI is allowed to provide data only at aggregated level. Personal data may sometimes be exchanged in projects.

For general public, georeferenced data (parcel geometry) would be a minimum. Researchers like to get data as detailed as possible.

2. What data do you think should not be shared and should only be used by Paying Agencies?

- What has made you feel this way/why do you think this way?

Personal data. Data about subsidies is also very sensitive.

In opposite, publishing parcels with their crops wouldn't harm anyone.

3. Who do you think most benefits from partially or open data sharing?

- Can you explain why you feel this way?

Scientists, business (in areas of crops).

Administrations (e.g. currently, the Plant Protection Inspection Service can't benefit from IACS data (may be for technical reasons)).

Make data available even if not yet validated. Timing is important.

Farmers: we have seen a presentation from Belgium explaining that data publication enable farmer to realize if they did wrong or outdated declaration and to correct or withdraw their demand.

4. Do you have any idea about how the process of data sharing from farmer to wider stakeholder groups can be improved?

Making data public is the first step but lots of other improvements are required:

- Portal: access point may be the PA portal and/or another one.
- Metadata : files should be well documented
- Clear structure of data : currently, IACS is rather complex, some mismatch between tables
- More harmonised data; common standard in Europe: it would facilitate analysis at European level.
- One single access point for farmers (PA – soil inspection ...), more integrated